

NOTES

Equilibrium Studies of the Magnesium-Hydrogen System in Mixed Solvents

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SSELECTIVITY coefficients have been measured at 25° for Mg^{2+} - H^+ system using Zeo-Karb 225 cation exchange. Methanol-water, ethanol-water and isopropanol-water mixtures were used at external solution concentration of 10, 20 and 30% (V/V). The total ionic strength of the medium was maintained at both 0.025 and 0.1M. If other conditions are comparable, the order of the selectivity coefficients in alcohol-water system is: isopropyl > ethyl > methyl alcohol. The uptake of each solvent mixture by both pure hydrogen resinate and pure magnesium resinate was determined. ΔF^* for each reaction was calculated.

Although many results of ion-exchange experiments in aqueous media have been published, there are very few literature references to ion-exchange in nonaqueous media or in mixed solvents. These studies revealed the role of the solvent on the ion-exchange process. The purpose of the present work was to compare ion-exchange equilibria of one pair of ions in nonaqueous media with those in aqueous media and to ascertain whether there was a relationship between these equilibria and the swelling of the resin.

Experimental

The ion-exchange resin Zeo-Karb 225 was sieved between 250-420 microns, that fraction which was used for all the experiments. The resin was subjected to hydrogen-sodium twice by treatment with 2M sodium chloride and 3N hydrochloric acid,

All the chemicals used were either of E. Merck GR or BDH Analar grade.

Equilibrium procedure: The experimental procedures for the equilibrium studies were identical with those used for similar studies in aqueous media¹.

Solvent uptake—The uptake of each solvent mixture by both pure hydrogen² resinate and pure magnesium resinate was determined experimentally.

The concentration of magnesium ion was determined titrimetrically with EDTA. The concentration of hydrogen ions was determined by titration against standard alkali.

Results and Discussion

The selectivity coefficient, K , is calculated for each exchange reaction from the equation

$$K = \frac{(mH^+)^2}{mMg^{2+}} \times \frac{\bar{N}Mg^{2+}}{(\bar{N}H^+)^2}$$

From the plots of equilibrium quotient vs. resin composition, it may be noted that at total ionic strength of 0.025M in pure aqueous solution, the selectivity coefficient values were always lower than unity all over the whole range of equivalent fraction, indicating that the resin is more selective to hydrogen ions than magnesium ions. On the other hand, as the methyl alcohol partially replaced the aqueous solution, such reversal in selectivity has disappeared and the affinity of the resin to magnesium ions is enhanced.

Such affinity is greatly increased by increasing the proportion of the alcohol, thus reaching its maximum value at 30% (V/V). As the ionic strength of the medium is increased up to 0.1M, the selectivity curves exhibited a similar behaviour, but to a slightly greater extent. At such concentration, there are two factors contributing together for the enhancement of the affinity of the resin to magnesium ions, one such factor is the increase in the ionic strength of the external solution, the other factor is the partial displacement of the pure aqueous solution by alcohol. In ethanolic solution when the ionic strength is maintained at 0.025M, the same effect on the selectivity coefficient has been obtained. The most interesting feature of the obtained curves is the close similarity in shape to that already found in methanolic solution at the same ionic strength, the only difference is that the present curves showed a slightly greater affinity of the resin for the studied cation. When the same proportions of ethanol were used at total ionic strength of 0.1M, a selectivity curve of much greater similarity to those previously obtained in methanolic solution, except that the 30% (V/V) curve exhibits a sharp maximum. Studying the effect of isopropanol on the selectivity of the resin, using the same three proportions of the solvent, maintaining the constant ionic strength at 0.025M, results in an affinity curve of great similarity to the corresponding curves in presence of either methanol or ethanol. A greater variation in the selectivity curves has been obtained

at total ionic strength of 0.1M, the selectivity coefficient reaches its maximum value e. g; $K_{\approx 36}$ at $N_{Mg^{++}}$ of 0.9, such value cannot be obtained in the presence of another two solvents.

It may be noted, therefore, that all the selectivity curves agreed well with the fact that there is an overall increase in the affinity of the resin towards magnesium ions, when organic solvent was added, and such affinity is further increased by increasing the proportion of the solvent employed. The presence of some organic solvent reduces the swollen volume of magnesium resinate, a fact which cannot be obtained for hydrogen resinate; the possibility of a relationship between swelling and selectivity is indicated. The increase in selectivity may be due in part to increase in the activity coefficient ratio f_{HRes}/f_{MgRes} caused by an increase in the concentration of the resin phase. A similar effect is observed in aqueous media in which the ionic strength of the external solution is increased from 0.025 to 0.1M, thereby reducing the swollen volume of the resin². The exchange data in methanol-water, ethanol-water and isopropanol-water mixtures reflect a greater selectivity of the ion-exchange resin for the metallic magnesium in the above solvent mixtures than in pure water.

In the above studied water alcohol mixtures, $\log k$ is seen in the figure to vary essentially linearly with $1/D$ as represented by other investigators⁴⁻⁷ for ion exchange in mixtures of water and another polar solvent; this proves that under the conditions studied, electrostatic ion interaction rather than changes in the ion solvation.

Oiwa's empirical treatment lends weight to the interpretation of the maximum as primarily a medium effect involving the proton and operative in both the resin and external phases. Due to the close similarity between methanol and ethanol, the selectivity maximum was observed in ethanol-water mixtures as well as in methanol-water mixtures. The maximum in the selectivity curve that was already found in ethanol-water mixtures was of higher magnitudes, than that in methanol-water mixtures, but it is proved to be located at higher values of equivalent fraction of the magnesium ion in the resin phase. It has been observed that, the selectivity maximum in isopropanol-water mixture will be significantly higher than those predicted in the presence of ethanol. The sharpness in the maximum has been increased by gradually increasing the proportion of alcohol to water up to 30% (V/V) alcohol; such phenomenon support the fact that the proton effect is remarkable by increasing the percentage of the added solvent. On the other hand, using 30% isopropanol at total ionic strength of 0.025M, no such maximum has been observed.

The free energy of activation was calculated for this exchange for each of the solvent compounds. It may be noted, however, that as the negativity of ΔF^* increases⁸, the tendency of the exchange

reaction to proceed from the hydrogen form of the resin to the magnesium form increases.

There are two points of particular interest in this exchange system. First, the amount of the solvent taken up by the resin decreased as long as it was converted to the magnesium form as can be seen in the table by comparing the values of solvent

TABLE—SOLVENT UPTAKE BY BOTH HYDROGEN AND MAGNESIUM RESINATES AT VARYING IONIC STRENGTHS AND SOLVENT COMPOSITION

Total ionic strength	Type of solvent	Solvent composition % of alcohol (V/V)	Solvent/lg resin	
			H resinate	Mg resinate
0.025	methanol-water	10	0.652	0.592
		20	0.594	0.480
		30	0.494	0.420
0.1	methanol-water	10	0.598	0.509
		20	0.502	0.488
		30	0.489	0.408
0.025	ethanol-water	10	0.500	0.492
		20	0.462	0.490
		30	0.402	0.379
0.1	ethanol-water	10	0.475	0.421
		20	0.400	0.378
		30	0.382	0.320
0.025	isopropanol-water	10	0.427	0.400
		20	0.399	0.366
		30	0.362	0.292
0.1	isopropanol-water	10	0.872	0.320
		20	0.956	0.282
		30	0.802	0.256

uptake at one and the same solvent composition and definite ionic strength. Secondly, it has been found that the order of solvent uptake, if other conditions are comparable, for both hydrogen and magnesium resins is methyl > ethyl > isopropyl alcohol, which is exactly the reverse of the order of selectivity coefficients under the same conditions. Thus it may be noted, however, that the increase in the total ionic strength of the external solution has the same influence at that of the organic solvent on the selectivity coefficient.

References

- O. D. BONNER and V. RHETT, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, 56, 954.
- O. D. BONNER and J. C. MOORFIELD, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, 58, 555.
- O. D. BONNER, W. J. ARGERSINGER and A. W. DAVIDSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 1044.
- T. SAKAKI and H. KAKIHANA, *Kagakw (Tokyo)*, 1953, 23, 471.
- G. M. PANCHENKOV, V. I. GORSHKOV and M. V. KIKLANOVA, *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1958, 32, 361.
- A. T. DAVYDOV and R. F. SKOLBIONOK, *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1958, 32, 1708.
- H. KAKIHANA and K. SEKIGUCHI, *Nippon Yakugaku Zasshi*, 1955, 75, 111.
- B. J. BIRCH, J. P. REDFERN and J. E. SALMON (Univ. Surrey, London) *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1967, 63, 2336.